

Analysis on Changes of Urban Land Use Patterns in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

Min Min Aye Than*, Yu Nandar Soe**, Mar Mar Khin***

Abstract

Dagon Myothit (South) Township which occupies the eastern part of Yangon City has an area of 79.4 square kilometer. It is located between latitudes 16° 46' 51" and 16° 49' 45" North and longitude 96° 11' E and 96° 13' East. This paper attempts to find out the factors that control the land use type development of urbanization pattern in Dagon Myothit (South) Township. According to this data, cultivated land has changed to industrial land, hence change in urbanization patterns. This study focuses on the area of urbanization patterns changes (2004-2005 to 2013-2014) due to the pressure of growing population. The main objectives of the paper are (1) To examine the physical and human bases factors of the study area (2) to analyze the classification of land use types in the study area and (3) to assess the development of the study area related to urbanization patterns. To the above objectives, official statistics related to population data and land use data are collected from Township Administrative Office and Land Records Department. Spatial change for urbanization patterns is analyzed by using Arc GIS 10.1 and field study. By using Microsoft Excel database, population growth and Land use pattern are analyzed. Thus it is found that the result of changes from agricultural land use to industrial land use and transportation land use is improvement in the study area. Dagon Myothit (South) Township has the positive effect of the transportation land use and Industrial Zone.

Key Words: Urban Land Use Patterns, Dagon Myothit (South) Township

Introduction

Study Area

The study area is Dagon Myothit (South) Township within Eastern Yangon District. There are 12 Townships in Eastern Yangon District. This township comprises 42 wards of which 32 wards are settled, but 10 wards are still unhabited.

Research Questions

What types of land use pattern are usually found in urban area of Dagon Myothit (South) Township?

How are the types of land use pattern changed in Dagon Myothit (South) Township?

Aim

The main aim of this research paper is to investigate the distribution of urban and land use pattern changes in Dagon Myothit (South) Township.

Objectives

Objectives of the research paper are;

- (1) To examine the physical and human bases factors of the study area
- (2) To analyze the classification of land use types in the study area and
- (3) To assess the development of the study area related to urbanization patterns.

* Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University

** Tutor, Department of Geography, Nationalist Youth Resource Development Degree Collage

*** Dr., Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University

Research Design

The research is composed of four portions. Portion one consists the physical bases of Dagon Myothit (South) Township and portion two is the analysis of social factors, focusing on population characteristic because population pressure influences the land use pattern changes. Portion three is a classification of urban and land use pattern. Finally presents finding and suggestion. The conclusion is based on the finding from the field surveys during which discussion and open talks are conducted with the residents in Dagon Myothit (South) Township.

Source of Data and Methodology

First, secondary data and information were collected from Libraries and Department. We have secondary data are climate data, population and current land use data, soil types and their properties data, type of urban, land use and crops grown data. Population and Current land use data are collected from Township Administrative Office, Soil types and their properties from Land Use Department, type of land use and data of crops grown from Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township. Second, changes of urban and land use patterns were observed for some wards. Land use changes were investigated from 2004-2005 to 2013-2014. Land use data are examined by map and diagrams combined with Geographical Information Systems (GIS).

I. Physical Factors

1.1 Location, Size, Shape and Boundaries

Dagon Myothit (South) Township is located in the north eastern part of Yangon City and included in East Yangon District in Figure 1.1. It lies between the floodplain of Bago River and the Ngamoeyeik Creek. Latitudinally it falls between 16° 46' 51" N and 16° 49' 45" N and longitudinally between 96° 11' E and 96° 13' E in Figure 1.2. The area of Dagon Myothit (South) is 79.4 square kilometres, representing 10.47 percent of the total area of Yangon City (755.403 square kilometers). The distance of boundaries between Hlegu Township on the North and Dagon Myothit (Seikkan) Township on the east is 16.4 kilometers. The boundary on the south is drawn by Thaketa Township, Thingangyun Township on the southwest and Dagon Myothit (East) Township on the west. As this boundary is marked along the Ngamoeyeik Creek, it can be classified natural boundary and its length is 2.6 km. The township now comprises 42 wards in Figure 1.3.

1.2 Relief and Drainage

As the study area, in fact, is part of the low plain built by the Ngamoeyeik Creek and the Bago River, there is distinctly flat land area. The study area is flat and low with a general elevation between 4.5 meter and 6.09 meter above sea level.

II. Social Factors

2.1 Population Growth

The number of populated was 262176 persons in 2005 and it increased to 315334 persons in 2014, giving a growth of 53164 persons within the decade. The yearly population growth in the 2005-2014 periods is shown in Table (2.1). The yearly increase and decrease in the number of population and respective growth are shown in Table (2.1).

Table 2.1 Total population of Dagon Myothit (South) Township (2005-2014)

Year	Population	Increase/ Decrease	(%)
2005	262170		
2006	262157	-13	-0.0004
2007	271889	9372	0.36
2008	284454	12565	0.45
2009	285293	839	0.02
2010	298669	13376	0.46
2011	298712	43	0.001
2012	298893	181	0.01
2013	297731	-1162	-0.03
2014	315334	17603	0.57

Source: Township General Administrative Office in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

2.2 Population Density and Distribution

According to the 2005 data, the total area of Dagon Myothit (South) Township was 79.4 square kilometres with a total population of 262130 people and density of 3301 persons per square kilometers in Figure 2.2. The most densely populated ward was Ward No.71 with a density is 2679.66 people per square kilometres. It is located on the southern part of the study area. The lowest density was Shantegyí with 158 people per square kilometres and located on the northern part of the study area.

According to 2014 data, total population was 315334 people and density of 3972 person per square kilometres. The most densely populated ward is No.54 with a density of 29162.06. The lowest population density is Shantegyí with 200 people per square kilometres, Ywarthargyi with 516 people per square kilometres in Figure 2.3. Figure 2.4 shows the wards with high population density are due to having the good communication, diverse economic activities, industrial zone and being close to the downtown.

During 10 years, the population has increased, but in unevenly distribution pattern. High population concentration areas are Ward No.18, 70, 19, 54, 107, 55, 20, 71, 56, 26, 53, 21, 22, 17, 72 and 104 because the population distribution depends on the urban facilities and transport condition. These wards are more located along the main road, road junction, near market and near industrial zone.

Lowest concentration areas are Shantegy, Thonegwa, Kyisu (West), 63, 64, Ywathargyi, Seikmwe (1), 57, 23, 140, Laydaungkan, 105, 25, 106, 65 and 24 wards. There are concentrated still difficulty communicate and have a farmland, but do not have industrial zone and they are away from the downtown in Figure 2.5 and 2.6.

Table 2.2 Total Population and Population Density in Dagon Myothit (South) Township (2005 and 2015)

No.	Ward No	Area(km ²)	Population (2005)	Population (2014)	Population Change (2005-2014)	Population Density (2005)	Population density (2014)	Density Change (2005-2014)
1	17	0.608	6341.0	10061.0	3720	10429.27	16547.69	6118.42
2	18	0.6	16503	19902	2899	27505	3233.67	1385.27
3	19	0.808	16798	16185	-613	20789.6	20030.94	-758.66
4	20	0.704	13563	14284	721	19265.62	20289.77	1024.15
5	21	0.621	8224	11915	3691	13243.15	19186.79	5943.64
6	22	1.661	9768	11393	1625	14777.6	6859.12	-7918.48
7	23	3.081	5937	5873	-64	1926.97	1906.19	-20.78
8	24	3.096	8391	9263	872	2710.27	2991.92	281.65
9	25	3.062	6855	8724	1869	2238.73	2849.12	610.39
10	26	3.049	11049	12714	1665	3623.81	4169.89	546.08
11	53	0.6	12323	12180	-143	20038.33	20300	261.67
12	54	0.543	12986	15835	2849	23915.28	29162.06	5246.78
13	55	0.774	5774	14754	8980	7459.94	19062.02	11602.08
14	56	0.704	13761	14083	322	19546.87	20004.26	457.39
15	57	0.647	4448	5821	1373	6874.8	8996.9	2122.1
16	63	0.254	2570	3075	505	10118.11	12106.29	1988.19
17	64	0.278	3658	3231	-427	13158.27	11622.3	-1535.97
18	65	0.774	5770	9901	4131	7454.78	12791.99	5337.21
19	70	0.6	16565	16970	405	2708.33	28283.33	25574.67
20	71	0.553	14818	14274	-544	26795.66	25811.93	-983.73
21	72	0.611	10195	10994	799	16685.76	17993.45	1307.69
22	104	0.53	8033	10941	2908	15156.6	20643.39	5486.79
23	105	0.517	5657	8382	2725	10941.97	16212.76	5270.79
24	106	0.694	4970	8949	3979	7161.38	12894.81	5733.43
25	107	0.634	11548	15170	3622	18214.51	23927.44	5712.93
26	140	0.507	7100	6662	-438	14003.94	13140.04	-863.9
27	Kyisu(west)	3.954	2188	2802	614	610.32	708.65	98.33
28	Ywathargyi	8.928	1995	4608	2613	225.29	516.13	290.84
29	Thonegwa	3.954	2342	2282	-60	592.31	577.14	-15.17

No.	Ward No	Area(km ²)	Population (2005)	Population (2014)	Population Change (2005-2014)	Population Density (2005)	Population density (2014)	Density Change (2005-2014)
30	Laydaungkan	8.928	6903	7312	409	773.18	818.99	45.81
31	Seikmwe(1)	4.973	3957	5377	1420	795.69	1081.23	285.54
32	Shantegyí	9.544	1510	1912	402	158.21	200.34	42.63
34	33	1.738	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
35	34	0.278	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
36	35	0.462	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
37	36	1.681	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
38	37	1.107	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
39	38	0.959	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
40	39	0.912	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
41	40	1.175	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
42	41	3.731	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Total		79.4	262130	315334	52844	3301.38	3971.46	670.08

Source: Township General Administrative Office in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

Figure 2.2 Population Density in the Study Area (2005)

Source: Based on Table 2.2

Figure 2.3 Population Density in the Study Area (2014)

Source: Based on Table 2.2

Figure 2.4 Changes of Population Density in the Study Area (2005 - 2014)

Source: Based on Table 2.2

Figure 2.5 Population Distribution in the Study Area in 2005

Source: Based on Table 2.2

Figure 2.6 Population Distribution in the Study Area in 2014

Source: Based on Table 2.2

III. Urban Land Use Types of Dagon Myothit (South) Township

3.1 General Land Use of Dagon Myothit (South) Township

Urban Land use types of Dagon Myothit (South) Township can be classified as follows;

1. Residential land use
2. Land use for Primary Production
3. Industrial land use
4. Commercial land use
5. Land use for Services
6. Government and Organization Land Use
7. Recreational Land Use
8. Transportation Land use
9. Unused Land

Table 3.1 shows above the mention land use categories of Dagon Myothit (South) Township in 2005 and 2014.

Table 3.1 Urban Land Use Types of Dagon Myothit (South) Township (2005-2014)

No.	Types of Land Use	2005		2014	
		Square kilometer	Percent	Square kilometer	Percent
1.	Residential land use	43.32	54.56	53.85	67.81
2.	Land used for Primary Production	29.32	36.96	18.32	23.08
3.	Industrial land use	3.01	3.79	3.01	3.79
4.	Commercial land use	0.16	0.19	0.25	0.31
5.	Land used for Services	0.11	0.15	0.18	0.23
6.	Government and Organization Land use	2.67	3.37	2.67	3.37
7.	Recreational Land Use	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.10
8.	Transportation Land use	0.73	0.91	0.81	1.03
9.	Unused Land	0.22	0.28	0.22	0.28
Total		79.4	100	79.4	100

Source: Land Record Department, Dagon Myothit(South) Township

1. Residential Land Use

Residential land use occupied about 43.32 and 53.85 square kilometers in 2005 and 2014 in Figure 3.1. These land use was increased 10.58 square kilometers or 13.32 percent from 2005 to 2014 in Figure 3.2. The change in residential land use is more evident after 1989-90. There are 87328 land plots, each measuring 12.19 meter x 18.28 meter. Of the total land plots, only 67218 land plots has been occupied for the residential land use, the remaining land plots are occupied by agricultural activities and industrial zone. Residential land plots

gradually expand and decrease the cultivated areas. The residential buildings vary in size, shape, and quality. Most of the buildings are wooden buildings. Some are brick buildings and double storey buildings with corrugated iron roof. In double-storey buildings, the ground floors are used for commercial purposes. Residential and commercial land uses are combined in the study area.

Figure 3.1 Spatial Distribution Patterns of Urban Land Use Types in the Study Area in 2005

Figure 3.2 Spatial Distribution Patterns of Urban Land Use Types in the Study Area in 2014

Sources: Land Record Department of Dagon Myothit (South) Township

2. Land Used for Primary Production

Land used for primary production in Dagon Myothit (South) Township was 29.32 and 18.32 square kilometers in 2005 and 2014 (Figure 3.3 and 3.4). Decreasing primary production area is due to population growth with residential area expansion in Figure 3.5. Agricultural lands are found in the north and northeastern parts. The cultivated areas are found in Kyisu, Ywathargyi, Laydaungkan, Seikmwe (1), Shantegy.

Figure 3.3 Spatial Distribution Patterns of Land Used for Primary Production in the Study Area in 2005

Figure 3.4 Spatial Distribution Patterns of Land Used for Primary Production in the Study Area in 2014

Sources: Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

Figure 3.5 Spatial Change for Primary Production to Residential Land Use in the Study Area in 2014

Sources: Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

3. Industrial Land Use

It has three industrial zones which cover about 3.01 square kilometres, which does not change in 2005 and 2014. The industrial zone was established in the study area in 1989-90 by the Yangon City Development Committee.

Zone (1) is located in No.23 Ward which covers 2.01 square kilometres and has 173 industries including various workhouse, women garment factories, food stuff factories, personal and household goods factories, saw-mill, building materials factories and fish canning factories. Zone (2) is located in No.63 Ward which covers 0.86 square kilometres and has 812 industries including car parts factories, value-added wood-based factories, rubber product factories, women garment factories, electrical factories, indigenous traditional medicines factories, print and paper production, plastic product factories and vehicles and machine

repairs. Zone (3) is located in No.64 Ward which covers 0.25 square kilometers and has 1509 industries including mostly iron products in Figure 3.6. There is a women garment factory in Thonegwa, making garment for export. There are a number of small-scale home industries.

Figure 3.6 Spatial Distribution Pattern of Industrial Land Use in the Study Area in 2005 and 2014

Sources: Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

4. Commercial Land Uses

It is mostly associated with residential land and scattered within the wards. Commercial land use is about 0.16 and 0.25 square kilometre in 2005 and 2014. Nearly all of them are clustered along the main road and streets. In the period from 2005 to 2014, commercial land use of the Dagon Myothit (South) Township has been increasing with the increasing population and gradually development of economic activities.

There are two banks and seven local markets and it is also principal commercial land use area of the study area. Besides, there are several small stores and shops which sell groceries, rice, foodstuffs, building materials, vehicle accessories, household goods, electrical goods, chemical products, gold smith and medicines etc. There are also restaurants, food-stalls and cold drinks and tea shops. Most of people living along the main roads use their residences

for commercial purposes. Generally, ground-floors are used for retail shops, restaurant, tea shops, cold drink and miscellaneous goods.

5. Land Used for Services

Land used for services activities in the Dagon Myothit (South) Township occupied about 0.11 and 0.18 square kilometre in 2005 and 2014 of the total area. These service activities are carried out within the compounds of residence as either separate buildings or attached to the main house. Most prominent services are tailoring services, motorcar workshops, private tuitions, computer training, beauty parlor, photo studios, book-lending shops, TV repair shops and private clinics. Water supply system and electricity are also including in the service activities. Most of them are scattered within the wards along the main roads.

6. Government and Organization Land Use

It is characterized by the religious buildings, educational institutes, government department and non-governmental organization covering about 2.67 square kilometers in 2005 and 2014. Religious buildings are 5 Pagodas, 1 Church, 8 Temples, 128 Monasteries and 31 Nunneries, educational institutions are 23 Basic Primary Schools, 14 Basic Middle Schools, 6 Basic High Schools, 14 Monastic Schools, 2 Universities in Dagon Myothit (South) Townships such as Institution of Economic (Ywathargyi) and University of Culture in Figure 3.7. Other governmental buildings are Fire Station, Police Station, Gas Station, Hospital, Clinic, and Township and Ward Administrative Offices within Dagon Myothit (South) Townships. These governmental departments are found along the Pyidaungsu Road. Besides, the township also has such non-governmental organization as Women's Affair Committee, Maternity Child Healthcare Organization, Ex-serviceman Organization, Fire Extinguishing Reserve Office and Red Cross Office.

Figure 3.7 Spatial Distribution Patterns of Government and Organization Land Use in the Study Area in 2005 and 2014

Sources: Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

7. Recreational Land Use

The place for recreational land use within urban area is very small. This type covers only about 0.09 square kilometres of the total land area in Figure 3.2 and 3.3. The township has one public park, one playground and one gymnasium. This public park located in Ward No.23 and playground and gymnasium occur in No.25 Ward. There are very few park and playground for children.

8. Transportation Land Use

It is covered about 0.73 and 0.81square kilometer in 2005 and 2014. Being a later developed town it has a systematic layout in grid patterns transportation network. Study area, main roads and streets are constructed systematically, generally having north-south and east-west alignments. Yatanarbon, Hlawkar, Pyitharyarand Minyeyawswar roads align north-south directions and Pyidaungsu Road, Kantharyar Road, Myeik Road and Maungmakan Road trend east-west directions.

No. (2) Yangon-Mandalay Highway Main Road is major road which runs from north to south and has the boundary line between Dagon Myothit (South) and Dagon Myothit (East) townships. The remainder inner roads and streets are connected from east to west and north to south within the study area. The residential areas are in rectangular shape surrounded by rectangular streets in Figure 3.8.

Buses are served daily and commuters travel within the study area as well as inter-urban. Transportation is being carried out by bus, cycles, trishaws and bicycles. During 2005-2014, the area used for transportation has increased because residential land use gradually expands with newly built roads.

Figure 3.8 Spatial Distribution Patterns of Transportation Land Use in the Study Area in 2014

Sources: Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

9. Unused Land

It consists of the land without building. These un-built vacant lands still remain in some ward of the urban area. Unused land of the study area is about 0.22 square kilometres of the study area. It is changes to industrial land use in future time in Figure 3.9.

This is due to the absence of buildings in their respective land plots. Most of the people did not build the houses until recently in their land plots, although they have received the permission for the new land plots of extension ward.

Summary, the Residential land use increases from land use for primary production in the study. In future, Industrial land use increases from the unused land because transportation network improves in the study area. Therefore, commercial land use is gradually development in the study area.

Figure 3.9 Spatial Changes from Unused Land to Industrial Land Use in the Study Area in 2014

Sources: Land Record Department in Dagon Myothit (South) Township

3.2 Factor Controlling On Urban Land Use

The main control factors of urban land use are the Government Policy. Remove the squatter settlements in different townships there new towns were established in 1989 under the State Law and Order Restoration Council (SLORC). Thus, Dagon Mythit (South) Township is developed.

Furthermore, the industrial zone of Dagon Mythit (South) Township was established in 1989-90 by the Yangon City Development Committee. The name of Zone (1) is located in No.23 Ward which covers 2.01 square kilometres and has 173 industries. Zone (2) is located in No.63 Ward which covers 0.86 square kilometres and has 812 industries. Zone (3) is located in No.64 Ward which covers 0.25 square kilometers and has 1509 industries

During 2005-2014, the area used for transportation has increased because residential land use gradually expands with newly built roads and more accessibility to others township and CBD. As the town has a well-planned layout, the types of land use are mostly systematic.

IV. Finding and suggestion

4.1 Finding

In this research paper was analyzed the urban and land use pattern of Dagon Mythit (South) Township by using Arc GIS 10.1 software was used in the analysis. To find out the land use pattern located relationship physical factors such as relief, drainage and human factors such as total population, population density and distribution. To collect the urban land use patterns in the study area has 9 categories. To analyzed the development of the study area related to industrial zones and transportation network more accessibility to others township and CBD.

4.2 Suggestion

The shape of township is rectangular, align from northeast to southwest. The southwestern part of township is more converted with residential building and various type of land use is found. The northern part of township is sparsely populated and has land use for primary production and unused land.

Topography of the study area is low and flat. It lies between floodplain of Bago River and Ngamoeyeik Creek. Thus, water logging occurs in the rainy season. There is no water-logging in the southern part of the township due to systematic land modification. However, water-logging is not uncommon in the northern part as the inhabitants take no effort to modify on raise the land.

It has three industrial zones. These zones are located in the southern part of township. The socio-economic development of the southern part is partly related to the industrial sector. Some factories and manufacturing plants have gradually established in the northern part. If a certain section of the northern part has become an industrial zone, the area will soon prosper and fill up with residential buildings and related infrastructure.

It is about 11.3 kilometres from the downtown of Yangon City. The southern part of township is fairly close to the downtown of Yangon City and it takes less time to get with fairly good public transport service. No.2 main road that has direct link with the downtown. The inhabitants have to use trishaw, motor-cycle or bicycle to get to their respective houses.

Therefore, more bus line should be established for speedy and speedy transport of passengers and freight and further economic development of the northern part.

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References

- Aye Aye Soe. (2013). **A Geographical study of the land use of Dagon Myothit Township**, (Unpublished M.A thesis, Department of Geography, Dagon University).
- Khin Thandar New. (1996). **The study of the changes in the urban land use of Lather Township**, (Unpublished M.A thesis, Department of Geography, University of Yangon)
- Mar Lar Aye. (2006). **Central buslines linking between Dagon Myothit (South) Township**, (Unpublished M.A thesis, Department of Geography, Dagon University).
- Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation. (2004). **Soil type and characteristic of Myanmar**, Published by Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department.
- Township General Administrative Department. (2014). **Register Book, Dagon Myothit (South) Township**, Dagon Myothit (South) Township.